

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND PHRASEOLOGICAL REPRODUCTION OF GENERAL ASSESSMENT CONCEPTS "GOOD" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Berdimuradova Surayyo Baxodirovna

Student of the Termez State Pedagogical Institute, majoring in foreign language and literature (Euro-English).

Annotation: *this article provides detailed information on the lexical-semantic and phraseological reproduction of concepts of good assessment in English and Uzbek*

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Theoretical foundations of comparative study of evaluative components in phraseological units with components of vertical space. The purpose of this chapter is to determine the theoretical basis for the study of the evaluative component of phraseological units with a component of vertical space. In this regard, the chapter includes linguistic foundations of evaluation research, its typology; analysis of value systems of different worldviews. It summarizes approaches to the study of the evaluation category, phraseological composition of the language. The chapter gives substantiation of the assessment typology used in the work and the methodology of describing phraseological units from the point of view of their evaluative nature is considered.

The first paragraph is "The concept of evaluation in language. The typology of verbal evaluations of vertically oriented space" contains an abstract review of the scientific literature on the problems of modeling evaluative meaning, which is of great interest to linguists not only from the point of view of choice linguistic means of forming evaluative semantics, but also in the light of the logical theory of constructing estimates that affect this choice. Summarizing observations for researchers, we can say that evaluation qualifies as a language category, since

different ways of expressing it constitute a group of linguistic elements characterized by semantic generality. At the same time, it is also a conceptual category, since the assessment includes a positive or negative judgment of a person about a particular object of reality, including, first of all, about another person.

Having studied the well-known interpretations of the concept of "evaluation" (Yu. D. Apresyan 1974, 1997; N. D. Arutyunova 1990; A. Vezhbitska 1993, 1997, 1999; E. M. Wolf 1979, 1985, 1988; A. A. Ivin 1970; T. V. Markelova 1993-1995; V. N. Telia 1981, 1986, 1988 and others), we formulated the following definition of the evaluation category in language: language evaluation is a verbal process, result and method of fixing the determination by a subject (person or group of people) of the significance or value of a certain object.

In this article, taking as a basis the classification of N. D. Arutyunova, we proposed our typology of verbal evaluations of vertically oriented space, which includes the following components:

1. Assessment of the emotional state (joyful □ sad, cheerful □ sad, happy □ unhappy).
2. Moral and ethical assessment (good □ evil, moral □ immoral).
3. Aesthetic evaluation (beautiful □ ugly, healthy □ sick).
4. Assessment of social status (poor □ rich, power □ subordination).
5. Assessment of the degree of intensity (much □ little, more □ less).
6. Assessment of the degree of difficulty (difficult situation)
7. Assessment of the degree of importance (significant, important)

The first five types of assessments characterize both the upper and lower spaces. Assessment of the degree of difficulty is present in semantics only the lower space. The semantics of the upper space can be described in terms of assessing the

degree of importance. Almost all members of the presented oppositions have an evaluative character and are projected onto the axiological axis (good/evil, good/bad). The rating sign "+" or "-" on the rating scale may change to the opposite in another historical period. A number of categories have an ambivalent character, including simultaneously opposed signs (for example, a solar eclipse, northern lights). On the basis of a set of binary signs, universal sign complexes are constructed, with the help of which the world is assimilated and described.

An attempt is being made to study in more detail the axiological aspects of the category of space in order to show how the human assessment of the category of space is changing within the framework of various historical cultures; to identify the characteristic features of space; to identify thematic groups that are representatives of vertically oriented space.

The paragraph contains a discursive analysis of three works "The Word about Igor's Regiment", "Gulliver's Journey" and "Gargantua and Pantagruel", which were chosen as an illustration of the perception of the world picture with points of view of the spatial category. Examining the evaluative attitude to the category of space at different stages of human development, it was concluded that each model of the world corresponds to its own space. For the mythopoetic model, as well as for the model of Modern times, the most preferred was a horizontally oriented space with a central binary opposition of one's own and another's, the levels of which were connected by a vertical axis. This axis allowed dividing the world horizontally into two opposites. The horizontal projection, in turn, allowed the vertical space is opposed to the top and bottom. In the Middle Ages, with the development of Christianity, vertical movement played a special role, which was explained by the religious and moral consciousness of man. In this era, two main concepts can be distinguished: the first is based on upward movement, the second is based on downward movement. This is explained by the change of ideals that occurs in the period from the XIII □ XIV centuries to the XVI century. The changes affecting the

public and individual consciousness could not but affect the linguistic picture of the world. Analysis of literary sources related to according to different historical times, he showed how the perception of the category of space by human consciousness is reflected in language.

Based on the main features of phraseological units, we proposed a common classification of phraseological units for three languages, which allows us to determine the necessary units for further research. Taking into account the peculiarities of the lexical and semantic structure, we have identified 3 main groups of phraseological units:

1. Phrasemes (phraseological merges, or idioms, phraseological units)
2. Phraseological combinations
3. Proverbs and sayings

One of the fundamental provisions of our work is the statement that the main components of phraseological meaning are sememes (N. F. Alefirenko, V. P. Arkhangelsky, M. M. Kopylenko, Z. D. Popova). The specificity of phraseological meanings is determined by its sememic structure (N. F. Alefirenko,). There are denotative and connotative sememes

The connotative sememe (A.V. Kunin, I. A. Sternin, V. N. Telia), which includes expressive, evaluative and emotional semes, is considered a significant component in the meaning of phraseology. The connotative aspect has a high specific weight in the meaning of the phraseological unit, and this is noted by many researchers.

Sources of research. The main sources of the research were materials collected by us from works of fiction, both in the original and in translation, primarily from English into Uzbek. The most important source in the study of this problem, we consider various dictionaries, both educational and academic, translated, explanatory and phraseological proper, the materials of which have been widely involved in the study. In order to provide the greatest coverage of the

material, in order to show the range of functioning of the FE, we have widely used other means, for example, media materials, and in some cases dialect phraseological units.

Methodology and methodology of the study. The direct writing of the work was preceded by the creation of a FE card file at the level of each language and, based on it, the compilation of a comparative card file in order to identify the similarities and differences of the studied languages in the field of FE.

The research methodology in some cases is of a comparative nature, in others the ordinariness of the methodology lies in the fact that the phraseological data of each language were studied separately. Comparative analysis is used when comparing the FE of the Uzbek language with English phraseological units corresponding to them in structure and semantics.

Theoretical provisions of linguistic works of English and Uzbek linguists served as methodological sources. However, with all this, preference was given to the comparative typological method, which can be found both in comparative analysis and in the mutual translation of Uzbek and English phrasemes, and stylistically neutral stratification layer, and figurative connotative.

Comparative study of the FE of English and Uzbek languages is aimed at revealing the essence of the phenomenon under study, revealing its specificity both in linguistic, systemic terms, and in speech functional. Therefore, the identification and description of the identities and differences between the studied units of English and Uzbek languages, the definition of equivalent relations between the compared languages is one of the most important aspects of the comparative study of these languages.

The main task that is set in this case when comparing is the establishment of equivalent relations in the compared languages, therefore, the identification of the main ways of correspondence between phraseological units. The phraseological composition combines various linguistic combinations that differ from each other,

as we discussed above when classifying FE according to semantics and grammatical structure, the degree of semantic cohesion of components, grammatical structure, stability, motivation, etc. As the comparison shows, in general, the study of equivalent relations between the FE of the compared languages leads to the identification of the following types of interlanguage relations: full and partial phraseological equivalents, full and partial phraseological analogues and non-equivalent FE. Such differentiation of FE in comparative study naturally proceeds from the criteria for identifying allomorphic and isomorphic characteristics at the phraseological level. It most vividly reflects the specific features of the compared languages in displaying the linguistic and national properties of both languages, since, despite the distant, but genetically related relations between the compared languages, the phraseology of the two languages has developed and is developing in different ways and under different conditions.

From the point of view of lexico-semantic analysis of the FE of the compared languages, we have carried out a classification of their phraseological material. At the same time, we were based on the classical classification system of Vinogradov V.V. and on the latest phraseological achievements in the Uzbek language. On this basis, in the modern Uzbek language, we have identified lexical and semantic groups: a) phraseological combinations; b) phraseological unities; c) phraseological coalitions, which also have similar correspondences in the field of phraseological turns of the English language.

In the structural aspect, along with the significant similarity of phraseological systems, there is a significant shift in the correlation of Uzbek and English phraseology. Although, in the phraseological fund of both these languages, it is possible to find FE corresponding in structure to sentences, phrases and ordinary combinations of words, however, one or another structural unit of one language does not always coincide with a similar unit of another language. As a result of such a structural discrepancy, English and Uzbek phraseological systems cannot

completely coincide in their nominative potentials and in the expressed range of meanings. This can easily be proved by the fact that a certain part of the phraseological system of each language correlates not with phraseology, but with the vocabulary of the compared language.

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